

Solution Chemistry in Fused Monochloroacetic Acid: Part VI. Redox Reactions in Fused Monochloroacetic Acid.

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Lead tetra-monochloroacetate and tin tetra-monochloroacetate have been isolated and used as oxidising agents for the determination of As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and Fe^{3+} . Iodine, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate have also been used as oxidising agents for the determination of above ions in fused monochloroacetic acid medium. The course of these redox reactions have been followed potentiometrically. Visual titrations without indicator are possible when iodine, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate in monochloroacetic acid are used as the titrant.

IN continuation of the study of the solvent properties of fused monochloroacetic acid¹⁻⁵, redox reactions have been examined with a view to explore the possibility of using fused monochloroacetic acid as a reaction medium for the estimation of certain ions. Lead tetra-monochloroacetate and tin tetra-monochloroacetate have been isolated and characterised as the products of solvolysis of red lead and tin tetraiodide in monochloroacetic acid and along with potassium dichromate, potassium permanganate and iodine have been successfully employed as oxidising agents. In the case of iodine, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate, visual titrations without any indicator have also been carried out. The results of these investigations are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Monochloroacetic acid, chlorides of arsenic (III), phosphorus (III) and antimony (III) were purified by well known methods. Tin(II) chloride was placed over phosphorus pentoxide in vacuum desiccator for 24 hr., it was then heated in current of dry hydrogen chloride gas with constant stirring for about 1 hr. The sample was cooled in vacuum to remove the excess of hydrogen chloride gas.

Preparation

Lead dioxide (4 g.) was heated with monochloroacetic acid (100 g.) in a three necked 250 ml flask fitted with a reflux condenser having a silica gel guard tube and with a dry nitrogen inlet tube at 120° for 3-4 hr. with constant shaking. About 25 ml of monochloroacetic anhydride was also added to the reaction mixture to remove water from the reaction mixture. White crystalline compound separated out. It was then repeatedly washed with hot benzene and finally dried over phosphorus pentoxide. (Found Pb=30.46%, Cl=19.56%; $Pb(CH_2ClCOO)$ requires Pb=30.39% Cl=29.86%), Chlorine was estimated by heating the compound with fusion mixture ($Na_2CO_3 + NaOH + sodium\ metal$) which ensured the complete conversion

of chlorine into sodium chloride. The contents were dissolved in distilled water and boiled with 5 ml of 2N HNO_3 . To this solution a known volume of excess of standard $AgNO_3$ was added and after digesting the precipitates were filtered in a weighed sintered crucible and filtrate was collected in a titration flask. Chlorine was estimated from the filtrate by Vohland's method. The crucible containing precipitates of $AgCl$ was tried at 110° and cooled. It was weighed and the difference gave the weight of $AgCl$ precipitates. Tin tetra-monochloroacetate was prepared by similar methods as tin tetra-acetate. Iodine, potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate were A. R. grade and were used as such without further purification.

All the solids were weighed by the method of difference and dissolved in a known weight of the solvent. Transference of the materials was, as far as possible, carried out in a dry box. potentiometric titrations were carried out with the help of a potentiometer (OSWA Vernier potentiometer Cat. No. 30070.) with an external scalamp galvanometer for end point detections. A modified saturated calomel electrode with a capillary in the lower part which was blocked with asbestos fiber to avoid free flow of liquid was used as a reference electrode. A platinum electrode was used as the indicator electrode.

General procedure : The titration cell was flamed dried and flushed with dry nitrogen for 1 hr. The cell was fitted with a microburette and the electrodes maintained at $93.5^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The titrant and the titrand both were prepared in monochloroacetic acid. After each addition of the titrant, the mixture was stirred for some time and the change in the emf of the solution was noted. During the titration, an atmosphere of dry nitrogen was maintained.

The strengths (mole/litre) of the various solutions used were as follows : (a) lead tetra-monochloroacetate 0.0068 M, (b) potassium dichromate 0.0093 M, (c) ceric (III) nitrate trihydrate 0.0058 M, (d) iodine 0.0084 M, (e) potassium permanganate 0.0076 M.

Results and Discussion

Redox reaction in non-aqueous solvents have been a topic of interest⁶⁻⁸. Paul and his coworkers⁹ and Waddington and his coworkers¹⁰ have carried out redox reactions in fluorosulphuric acid and liquid hydrogen chloride respectively. Lead tetraformamide and trilead octaformamide have been used as oxidising agents in formamide¹¹. Solutions of cobalt(III) salts are strong oxidising agents in acetic acid solution and can oxidise ferrous, arsenic (III), antimony (III) and iodides and chlorine dioxide has been used for potentiometric titrations of the iodide ion in acetic acid solution¹². Dichloramine T can be used electrometrically and visually for the determination of ferrous, stannous, ascorbic acid and iodide ions¹³.

Lead tetra-monochloroacetate and tin tetra-monochloroacetate are white solids which turn black on exposure to moisture. They are sufficiently soluble in monochloroacetic acid to be used as oxidising agents. The solutions of lead tetra-monochloroacetates cannot be stored for more than 24 hr. as it turns grey and loses its oxidising power. The solutions of tin tetra-monochloroacetate can be stored for longer periods (a week). The solubility of potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate in monochloroacetic acid is quite low, however, solution upto 0.0064 molalities could be prepared which are quite stable for long periods.

Lead tetra-monochloroacetate as oxidising agent

When a solution of lead tetra-monochloroacetate in fused monochloroacetic acid is titrated with a solution of tin(II), antimony(III) or arsenic(III) phosphorus(III) chloride in the same solvent, there is a gradual decrease in the emf of the solution until a large drop in the potential appears when the molar ratio lead tetra-monochloroacetate to metal chloride reaches 1 : 1, thereafter the change in emf gradually decreases and ultimately becomes constant. Reverse titrations are also satisfactory. The product of solvolysis of tin(II) chloride and monochloroacetic acid i. e. $\text{Sn}(\text{CH}_2\text{ClCOO})_2$. $2\text{CH}_2\text{ClCOOH}$ is also oxidised by lead tetra-monochloroacetate in monochloroacetic acid solution. The curves for the titration are shown in Fig. 1. These observations may be explained on the basis of the following redox reactions :

There is only one flux in these titrations and thus rule out the possibility of any intermediate oxidation states of these elements. No attempt has been made to isolate the oxidised products. Similarly redox reactions have been carried out with tin tetra-monochloroacetate against these compounds. As before a large drop in the potential is observed when the molar ratio of tin

tetra-monochloroacetate to metal chloride reaches 1 : 1, similar types of the redox reactions can be proposed for this oxidising agent.

Fig. 1 : Redox reactions in fused monochloroacetic acid.

When a solution of lead tetra-monochloroacetate in monochloroacetic acid is added to the solution of cerium(III) nitrate the potential shift at the end point is again very sharp. This is observed at the cerium nitrate-lead tetra-monochloroacetate molar ratio 2 : 1 as would be expected by the reaction :

Redox reactions have also been carried out against cobalt(II) and nickel (II) acetates. The influx in the potential of the system at the molar ratio 2 : 1 suggests that both cobalt and nickel are oxidised to (+3) oxidation states. They could not be oxidised further :

Similar titrations were carried out using tin tetra-monochloroacetate as an oxidising agent. The results were quite satisfactory and the end point was shown by a sharp fall of potential. These observations can be explained on the basis of following reactions :

The results are given in Fig 2.

Fig. 2: Tin tetramonochloroacetate as oxidising agent in monochloroacetic acid.

Iodine as oxidising agent—Iodine is fairly soluble in monochloroacetic acid when its solution in monochloroacetic acid is added to the solution of antimony(III) or arsenic(III) and phosphorus(III) chlorides in the same solvent; there is an increase in the emf of the system. The rate of change of emf is maximum at the iodine-metal chloride molar ratio 1 : 2. The oxidation-reduction reaction obviously follow their normal course and have been found to proceed to completion in the presence of 1—2 g of sodium bicarbonate.

Iodine solution also oxidises tin(II) chloride, ferrous chloride and sodium thiosulphate in monochloroacetic acid and the end point is indicated by a sharp change in the emf of the system at 1:2 and 1:1 molar ratio of iodine versus tin(II) chloride and iron(II) chloride or sodium thiosulphate respectively.

Redox titrations against iodine can be followed visually also. Iodine solutions in monochloroacetic acid has been found to be an excellent titrant in redox titrations and do not require any indicator. The end point is detected by the appearance of a permanent faint yellow colour of iodine. Table 1 indicates the use of iodine solution for the titration of various reductants. As in aqueous medium, the potentiometric as well as visual titrations with iodine as an oxidising agent in monochloroacetic acid requires the presence of a small amount of sodium bicarbonate for the determination of arsenic and antimony.

TABLE 1—VISUAL TITRATIONS WITH IODINE SOLUTIONS IN FUSED MONOCHLOROACETIC ACID.

Compound	Wt. taken (g.)	Volume of I ₂ solution (ml)	Volume Required (ml)	Error (%)
SnCl ₂	0.0682	4.58	4.56	+0.43
AsCl ₃	0.0708	3.96	3.91	-0.50
SbCl ₃	0.0596	6.04	6.08	-0.66
PCl ₃	0.0616	5.72	5.80	-1.39
FeCl ₂	0.0954	5.38	5.40	-0.37
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	0.0876	6.02	5.78	+3.98

Potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate as oxidising agents : A solution of potassium dichromate in monochloroacetic acid is quite stable even after a week and has the oxidising power and has been used to oxidise arsenic(III), antimony(III), phosphorus(III) and tin(II) as chlorides. If the dichromate solution is titrated with the reductant, there is no perceptible change in the emf. of the solution in the beginning. On further addition, the emf. of the solution begins to decrease until a big potential drop is observed as potassium dichromate/metal chloride molar ratio 2 : 3 is reached. The colour of the solutions after these titrations become green suggesting that chromium is present in (+3) oxidation state. Reverse titrations have also been carried out and the jumps in the potential of the system near the end points are quite high. The course of the reactions may be explained by the following equations :

An oxidation-reduction reaction in monochloroacetic acid with the help of potassium permanganate and dichromate is slightly different from the same reaction in aqueous medium as no mineral acid is required. Similarly in the case of potassium permanganate is added the metal(III) chloride in monochloroacetic acid solution. A large drop in the potential of the system at the molar ratio potassium permanganate/metal(III) chloride 2 : 5 suggests that the following possible reaction take place :

It is observed that as compared to potassium dichromate solutions, potassium permanganate solution in monochloroacetic acid is not very stable and the colour changes near the end point are not very sharp.

the end points are very sharp and the redox reactions are reversible. Table 2 includes the results of the titrations of potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate against various reductants.

TABLE 2—VISUAL TITRATIONS WITH PERMANGANATE AND POTASSIUM DICHROMATE IN FUSED MONOCHLOROACETIC ACID.

Compound	Wt. taken (g.)	Volume of K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ solution used (ml)	Volume Required (ml)	Error (%)
Potassium Permanganate				
SnCl ₂	0.0721	5.28	5.27	+0.19
AsCl ₃	0.0759	4.32	4.30	+0.46
PCl ₃	0.0582	5.90	5.93	-0.51
SbCl ₃	0.0628	6.82	6.80	+0.29
Potassium dichromate				
SnCl ₂	0.0738	5.59	5.57	+0.35
PCl ₃	0.0612	6.28	6.29	-0.15
AsCl ₃	0.0779	5.21	5.20	+0.19
FeCl ₂	0.0829	4.90	4.95	-1.02

As in the case of iodine, visual titrations between the solutions of potassium permanganate and potassium dichromate in monochloroacetic acid and various oxidising agents have been carried out. In the case of potassium permanganate, the end points are not very sharp, however, in the case of potassium dichromate,

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